

**STUDIES ON SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION AND BIOLOGICAL
EVALUATION OF 2-(4-SUBSTITUTED-3-METHOXYBENZYL)-5,6-DIMETHOXY-
2,3-DIHYDRO-1H-INDEN-1-ONE DERIVATIVES**

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ABSTRACT:

A novel series of 2-(4-Substituted-3-methoxybenzyl)-5,6-dimethoxy-2,3-dihydro-1H-inden-1-one derivatives have been synthesized, characterized by using spectral data and screened for anti-tuberculosis activity. The anti-tubercular activity of the synthesized compounds (8a-f) was determined by microplate alamar blue assay and the outcomes were screened *in vitro* against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H37Rv strain. Compounds 8a-f exhibited good to potent anti-tubercular activity when compared with the standard first line anti-tuberculosis drugs (ciprofloxacin, pyrazinamide and streptomycin). Some of the tested compounds exhibited highest inhibitory activity at 1.6 µg/mL minimal inhibition concentration.

KEY WORDS: Indene derivatives, anti-tubercular activity and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H37Rv strain.

INTRODUCTION:

Tuberculosis (TB) is an intercellular pathogen that infects, perseveres and reproduces in immune cells, which is endemic in several regions of the world and pursues to be a prime global health issueⁱ⁻ⁱⁱⁱ. During the treatment of TB, the *M. tuberculosis* undergoes mutational changes and develops drug resistant pathogens which contributes to the elevated morbidity and mortality^{iv-v}.

Scheme-1

2-(4-Substituted-3-methoxybenzyl)-5,6-dimethoxy-2,3-dihydro-1H-inden-1-one derivatives (8a-f)

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The solvents were purified according to standard procedures prior to use, and all commercial chemicals were used as received. For thin-layer chromatography (TLC) analysis, Merck pre-coated Plates (silica gel 60 F254) were used and eluting solvents are indicated in the procedures. Merck silica gel 60 (230-400 mesh) was used for flash column chromatography. Melting point (mp) determinations were performed by using Mel-temp apparatus and are uncorrected. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian Unity instrument at room temperature at 400 MHz. Chemical shifts are reported in 'δ' parts per million (ppm) downfield from tetramethylsilane (TMS) with reference to internal solvent and coupling constants 'J' in Hz. The mass spectra were recorded on Agilent ion trap MS (Scheme 1). All the alkyl and acid chlorides used for the preparation of 8a-f were purchased from commercial sources.

Synthesis of (E)-3-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)acrylic acid (2)

To a solution of 10g (0.06024 mol) of 3, 4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde in 30 mL pyridine, 13.783 g (1.325 mol) of malonic acid and 1mL of piperidine were added. The resulting mixture was stirred at 105 °C to 110 °C for 6-8 h. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was cooled to 25 °C to 30 °C and slowly quenched the reaction mixture into 100 mL of 5% sodium hydroxide solution at 25 °C to 30 °C (pH: 9-10). The reaction mixture was washed with ethyl acetate (2 x 50 mL) and the organic layer separated was washed with 20 mL of 5% sodium hydroxide solution. The aqueous layers were combined and cooled to 15 °C to 20 °C. The aqueous layer was acidified slowly with 25 mL of 50% sulphuric acid below 20 °C (pH: 1-2). After an additional 30-45 min stirring at 15 °C to 20 °C, the solid obtained was collected by filtration, washed with 100 mL of water followed by 40 mL of n-hexane. The partially dried compound was unloaded into trays and dried at 55 °C to 60 °C for 8-10 h to give 11.10 g of the title compound. **Yield:** white solid (88%); **¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400MHz):** δ 7.743 (d, 1H, ArH), 7.211 (d, 1H, ArH), 7.133 (s, 1H, ArH), 6.88 (d, 1H, ArCH-), 6.33 (d, 1H Sp²CH-), 3.930 (s, 6H, CH₃); **MS (ES⁺):** m/z 209.08.

Synthesis of 3-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)propanoic acid (3)

To a solution of 15 (1.0 g, 4.8 mmol) in absolute ethanol (100 mL) was added Pd/C, and it was hydrogenated at 30 psi H for 30 min. The reaction was filtered over solka floc, and the filtrate was concentrated to yield a white solid that was dried in the vacuum oven. **Yield:** 100%; mp 95-97°C; **¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400MHz):** δ 11.20 (s, 1 H), 6.813-6.793 (m, 2H, ArH), 6.764-6.740 (m, 1H, ArH), 3.870 (s, 3H, CH₃), 3.859 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.912(t, 2H, ArCH₂-), 2.672 (t, 2H, -CH₂-); **MS (ES⁻):** m/z 209.9.

Synthesis of 5,6-dimethoxy-2,3-dihydro-1H-inden-1-one (4)

Added trifluoromethan sulfonic acid (3 eq) gently to a cooled (0 °C) solution of a 3-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)propanoic acid (0.5 mmol) in dry dichloromethane (1.0 mL) in a 12 mL Q-Tube pressure tube. Raise the temperature to room temperature. Placed a Teflon septum on the top of the tube and use the cap with a pressure adapter. Heated the mixture in an oil bath at 80 °C. Monitored the reaction by TLC and GC/MS. Poured the mixture into ice and extracted three times with dichloromethane. Dried the organic phase collected on Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrate under vacuum. Separated the product from the crude by flash chromatography. **Yield:** 95%; mp 118-120°C; **¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400MHz):** δ 7.187 (s, 1H, ArH), 6.901 (s, 1H ArH), 3.973 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.913 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.060 (t, 2H, ArCH₂-), 2.668-2.696 (m, 2H, COCH₂-); **MS (ES⁺):** m/z 193.20.

Synthesis of (Z)-2-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-5,6-dimethoxy-2,3-dihydro-1H-inden-1-one (6)

Dissolved 0.5 g of 5,6-dimethoxy-2,3-dihydro-1H-inden-1-one into 10 mL methanol in a round bottom flask. Added the 10mL of 10% methanolic KOH to this solution drop wise on ice bath. Dissolved 0.65 g of benzaldehyde derivative in 8 mL methanol and added to reaction mixture. Allowed the reaction mixture to stirred at ice bath for 30 minutes and afterwards at room temperature for 12 h. Evaporated the solvent followed by drop wise addition of dilute HCl. Adjusted pH of the content to acidic. Extracted the content with ethyl acetate. Separated the organic layer. Dried the residue over anhydrous sodium sulphate (Na₂SO₄) and concentrate. Purify the crude material by crystallization by methanol. **Yield:** 90%; mp 141-142°C; **¹H NMR(CDCl₃, 400 MHz):** δ 9.678(s, 1H, OH), 7.382 (s, 1H, ArH) 7.332(d, 1H, ArH), 7.227 (d, 2H, ArH), 6.895(d, 1H, ArH), 4.106(d, 1H, CH), 4.00 (s, 2H, ArCH₂), 3.911 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.877(s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.842 (s, 3H, OCH₃); **MS (ES⁺):** m/z 326.12.

Synthesis of 2-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzyl)-5,6-dimethoxy-2,3-dihydro-1H-inden-1-one (7)

Take 0.5 g of 2-benzylidene indanocine derivative in 10 mL of dry dimethylformamide. Added 0.1 g of 10% palladium-charcoal to the stirred solution. Supplies hydrogen gas through a balloon via syringe, after 2 hours. Added 0.5 g of palladium-charcoal again to the mixture. Stir the reaction further for 4 hours at room temperature. Filter the mixture carefully through Celite (filter aid). Wash the mixture with 5 mL of 5% dil. HCl. Extracted the mixture twice with 20 mL of ethyl acetate. Wash pooled organic fraction with water. Dry the mixture over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and distill the mixture under vacuum to obtain a crude mass. Charge the residue on a silica gel column to obtain 2-benzylindanocine derivative. Recrystallize the residue from chloroform-hexane to obtain 2-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzyl)-5,6-dimethoxy-2,3-dihydro-1H-inden-1-one. **Yield:** 92%; mp 138-141°C; ¹H NMR(CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.195 (s, 1H, ArH), 6.789 (dd, 2H, ArH), 6.727 (s, 1H, ArH), 6.723 (s, 1H, ArH), 5.498 (s, 1H, OH), 3.945 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.916 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.858 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.294-3.248 (m, 2H, ArCH₂), 2.958-2.934 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.657-2.597 (m, 1H, CH); **MS (ES⁺):** m/z 329.96.

Synthesis of 2-(4-Substituted-3-methoxybenzyl)-5,6-dimethoxy-2,3-dihydro-1H-inden-1-one derivatives (8a-f)

2-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzyl)-5,6-dimethoxy-2,3-dihydro-1H-inden-1-one (8.00 g, 0.058 mol) was treated with K₂CO₃ (0.064 mol), various halogenated compounds (0.058 mol) in acetone (100 mL) and the reaction mixture was heated to reflux over a period of 4 h. The white inorganic solid was filtered off and washed with EtOAc (100 mL). Removal of the solvents and subsequent distillation in vacuo (93 °C; 1.3 × 10 mbar).

4-((5,6-dimethoxy-1-oxo-2,3-dihydro-1H-inden-2-yl)methyl)-2-methoxyphenyl benzoate (8a)

Yield: 89%; ¹H NMR(CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 8.206 (dd, 2H, ArH), 7.631 (t, 1H, ArH), 7.507 (t, 2H, ArH), 7.260 (s, 1H, ArH), 7.069 (d, 1H, ArH), 6.905-6.842 (m, 2H, ArH), 3.961 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.925 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.796 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.384 (dd, 1H, CH), 3.130 (q, 1H, CH₂), 3.024-2.980 (m, 1H, CH₂), 2.807 (dd, 1H, ArCH₂), 2.687 (q, 1H, ArCH₂); **MS (ES⁺):** m/z 433.19.

4-((5,6-dimethoxy-1-oxo-2,3-dihydro-1H-inden-2-yl)methyl)-2-methoxyphenyl acetate (8b)

Yield: 90%; ¹H NMR(CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.201 (s, 1H, ArH), 6.856-6.789 (m, 3H, ArH), 3.950 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.894 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.807 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.352 (dd, 1H, CH), 3.107 (q, 1H, CH₂), 2.940-3.003 (m, 1H, CH₂), 2.779 (dd, 1H, ArCH₂), 2.641 (q, 1H, ArCH₂); **MS (ES⁺):** m/z 371.19.

2-(4-(benzyloxy)-3-methoxybenzyl)-5,6-dimethoxy-2,3-dihydro-1H-inden-1-one (8c)

Yield: 93%; ¹H NMR(CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.442-7.260 (m, 5H, ArH), 7.194 (s, 1H, ArH), 6.796 (d, 3H, ArH), 6.691 (dd, 1H, ArH), 3.972 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.914 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.859 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.279 (dd, 1H, CH), 3.069 (q, 1H, CH₂), 2.972-2.929 (m, 1H, CH₂), 2.762 (dd, 1H, ArCH₂), 2.62 (q, 1H, ArCH₂); **MS (ES⁺):** m/z 419.32.

2-(4-(3-bromopropoxy)-3-methoxybenzyl)-5,6-dimethoxy-2,3-dihydro-1H-inden-1-one (8d)

Yield: 92%; δ 7.197 (s, 1H, ArH), 6.839-6.735 (m, 4H, ArH), 4.127 (t, 2H, -OCH₂), 3.944 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.916 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.828 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.627 (t, 2H, BrCH₂-), 3.287 (dd, 1H,

CH), 3.081 (q, 1H, CH₂), 2.990-2.937 (m, 1H, CH₂), 2.772 (dd, 1H, ArCH₂), 2.640 (q, 1H, ArCH₂), 2.380-2.319 (m, 2H, -CH₂); **MS (ES⁺):** m/z 451.13.

4-((5,6-dimethoxy-1-oxo-2,3-dihydro-1H-inden-2-yl)methyl)-2-methoxyphenyl 2-nitrobenzenesulfonate (8e)

Yield: 94%; 8.058 (dd, 1H, ArH), 7.847-7.780 (m, 2H, ArH), 7.725-7.683 (m, 1H, ArH), 7.174 (s, 1H, ArH), 7.133 (d, 1H, ArH), 6.823-6.758 (m, 3H, ArH), 3.951 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.912 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.526 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.296 (dd, 1H, CH), 3.094 (q, 1H, CH₂), 2.974-2.912 (m, 2H, ArCH₂), 2.761-2.667 (m, 2H, CH₂); **MS (ES⁺):** m/z 514.16.

4-((5,6-dimethoxy-1-oxo-2,3-dihydro-1H-inden-2-yl)methyl)-2-methoxyphenyl 3-nitrobenzenesulfonate (8f)

Yield: 95%; 8.745 (t, 1H, ArH), 8.507-8.479 (m, 1H, ArH), 8.229 (d, H, ArH), 7.732 (t, 1H, ArH), 7.180 (t, 2H, ArH), 6.840-6.800 (m, 2H, ArH), 6.721 (d, 1H, ArH), 3.957 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.917 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.514 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.300 (dd, 1H, CH), 3.092 (q, 1H, ArCH₂), 2.968-2.905 (m, 1H, ArCH₂), 2.737-2.637 (m, 2H, CH₂); **MS (ES⁺):** m/z 514.17.

Anti-tubercular activity

The *in vitro* anti-tubercular assessment of 8a-f have been tested against Mycobacterium tuberculosis H37Rv strain ATCC 27294 using the microplate alamar blue assay (MABA) and ciprofloxacin, pyrazinamide, streptomycin as standard drugs [29]. All the compounds 6a-l are screened for anti-tubercular activity in three sets (n=3). Initially, to lessen the evaporation of the medium in the aseptic 96 well plates during incubation, 200 µL of sterile deionized water was placed on all outer circumference wells of plate. Then to each well, 100 µL of the Middlebrook 7H9 broth was added and serial dilutions of the compounds 6a-l were made directly on the plate (i.e., 100-0.8 µg/mL). Then the 96 well plates was accurately occluded with parafilm and incubated at 37°C for five days. Finally, 25 µL of freshly prepared combination of almar blue (Accumed International, Westlake Ohio) reagent and 10% tween 80 (1:1) were added to the well plate and incubated for one day. A blue and pink colour was elucidated as no bacterial growth and growth respectively. The Minimal Inhibition Concentration (MIC) is the lowest drug concentration, which averted a colour change from blue to pink.

Table-1: *In vitro* anti-tubercular activity of the 6a-l against *M. tuberculosis* H37RV strain.

Compound	Substituents (R)/ Structure	MIC* values (µg/mL)
8a	C ₆ H ₅ CO-	3.1
8b	CH ₃ CO-	1.5
8c	BrCH ₂ CH ₂ -	2.1
8d	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ -	3.9
8e	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ SO ₂ -	2.2
8f	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ SO ₂ -	4.2
Ciprofloxacin		3.125

Pyrazinamide		3.125
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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All the synthesized compounds were evaluated for *in vitro* anti-tubercular against *M. tuberculosis* and the results were tabulated in Table 1. Compounds 8b were very potent against *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv strain at MIC 1.6 µg/mL. Compounds 8a, 8c and 8e showed less activity as that of standard drugs (pyrazinamide, ciprofloxacin) with a MIC 3.125 µg/mL. The compound 8f and 8d was found to be active against *M. tuberculosis* strain at MIC of 3.125 µg/mL high to MIC of standard drugs Pyrazinamide and Ciprofloxacin.

It was found that compounds substituted with *m*-nitro at R exhibited potent anti-tubercular activity, while remaining derivatives showed good anti-mycobacterial activity. Based on structural similarities with the first line anti-tuberculosis drugs (i.e., rifampicin), the synthesized compounds may act by inhibiting bacterial RNA polymerase (enzyme essential for DNA transcription) [30].

CONCLUSION

In this study, novel 2-(4-Substituted-3-methoxybenzyl)-5,6-dimethoxy-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-inden-1-one derivatives were designed, synthesized and screened for anti-tubercular activity against *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv strain. The structures of the synthesized compounds were characterized by ¹H NMR and Mass spectroscopic results. All compounds screened for anti-TB activity using MABA, the compounds **8a-f** showed anti-tubercular activity within MIC range of 1.6 to 6.25 µg/mL, more or equivalent to those for standard anti-Tb drugs (pyrazinamide, ciprofloxacin with MICs 3.125 µg/mL). From the above results, due to the presence of novel structure and potent anti-tubercular activity it can be concluded that the tested compounds could be a best initiation to find new lead to class of anti-tubercular agents in the future.

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